
How the Pharmaceutical Industry Influences the Production of Scientific Evidence: Research Manipulation and Ghostwriting

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Note: This science communication piece is based on the article “*Influence, Deviations, and Excesses in the Pharmaceutical Sector*” [1], authored by the same researcher, and derives from the doctoral dissertation “*The Consolidation of the Pharmaceutical Sector in the Global Economy: Growth, Influence, Deviations, and Marketing*” [2].

The global rise of the pharmaceutical industry

Over the last century, since Alexander Fleming’s discovery of penicillin in 1928, the pharmaceutical sector has undergone profound productive, organizational, and political transformations [2]. Companies that were initially small—often family-run and restricted to local markets [3]—gave way to large multinational corporations valued at hundreds of billions of dollars [4], with global reach [5] and growing influence over scientific agendas, clinical practices, and regulatory arenas [1, 2, 5].

This process of expansion resulted from the combination of scientific and technological advances—such as the development of new medicines [6, 7, 8]—and broader socioeconomic transformations, including accelerated urbanization, industrial growth, mass production, rising per capita income, expanded access to health systems, and higher levels of education [9, 10]. Together, these factors increased demand for pharmaceuticals and consolidated their centrality as a recurrent response to health problems across diverse social contexts [2].

Beyond these widely recognized drivers, critical scholarship has highlighted the sector’s adoption of controversial practices of corporate influence, synthesized in the article “*Influence, Deviations, and Excesses in the pharmaceutical sector*” [1]. These practices are organized into eight major analytical categories: (i) lobbying and campaign financing; (ii) influence over regulatory and oversight bodies; (iii)

influence in patient organizations; (iv) influence in the drafting of clinical guidelines; (v) manipulation, selective promotion, and concealment of research and drug trials; (vi) ghostwriting; (vii) strategies of diagnostic expansion and disease promotion (disease mongering); and (viii) financing and the provision of benefits to prescribers and institutions, including psychosocial mechanisms and formative dimensions.

Far from being limited to isolated misconduct, these mechanisms operate structurally and in institutionalized ways, producing cumulative effects on public policies, regulatory processes, the production and circulation of scientific evidence, clinical guidelines, and therapeutic decision-making.

This scientific report focuses on two of these dimensions: (v) “manipulation, selective promotion, and concealment of research and drug trials” and (vi) “ghostwriting.” Drawing on empirical evidence and case studies, it examines – synthetically and accessibly – how these mechanisms operate and their implications for clinical practice, the production and circulation of scientific evidence, and collective health within contemporary health systems.

Manipulation, promotion, and concealment of research and drug trials

For a new drug to be discovered, introduced, and consolidated in the pharmaceutical market, its trajectory is expected to rest on scientific evidence validated by the international academic community. In general terms, testing begins at the preclinical stage under laboratory conditions and subsequently in animals; only then does it proceed to extensive clinical trials in humans. This is a lengthy process requiring meticulous documentation, administrative procedures, and time, with a central purpose: ensuring maximum safety for future users and patients.

Once completed, trial results are typically published as scientific articles, which may then be included in meta-analyses (statistical methods that aggregate results from two or more independent studies) and systematic reviews (investigations that compile relevant studies addressing a specific question). When disseminated in scientific journals, these outputs circulate among thousands of health professionals, reinforcing the legitimacy and acceptance of the drug as a high-quality product.

In contemporary practice, however, one point is particularly salient: the pharmaceutical industry is the leading funder of drug trials worldwide [11]. Studies on efficacy are often conducted by the company itself or by consultants, researchers, and university groups financed by it. Although many pharmaceutical innovations have improved health and quality of life, this configuration has also been associated, in some contexts, with ambiguous relationships and conflicts of interest involving industry, researchers, and academic institutions.

A systematic review by Bekelman et al. (2003), covering 1,140 studies published between January 1980 and October 2002, found that economic relationships between industry, researchers, and academic institutions are widespread and that conflicts arising from these connections have significantly affected biomedical research outcomes [12]. Similarly, Lexchin et al. (2003), examining research published between January 1966 and December 2002, observed that industry-funded studies were more likely to report results favorable to sponsor products than studies funded by other sources, such as government [13]. Since then, multiple articles, systematic reviews, and meta-analyses – using diverse methodologies and approaches – have suggested that pharmaceutical funding can introduce bias into research [11, 14, 15, 16, 17].

But how might a company distort a scientific study? A recurrent theme in this debate is the presence of a systematic set of biases aligned with sponsor interests, which can emerge as early as the planning and conduct of trials. When evaluating a new medicine, researchers may select inferior comparators instead of reference drugs [18], use inappropriate comparator dosages [11], or even employ placebo controls [19]. Such strategies can obscure the drug’s true performance and potential side effects relative to competitors, increasing the likelihood of favorable outcomes – at the cost of serious ethical negligence toward trial participants and future users.

Another bias identified in the literature is the tendency to prioritize sponsorship for therapies already viewed as potential “winners” [12]. This is followed by practices such as selective publication of favorable findings and reduced visibility – or complete absence – of unfavorable results [12, 13]. Results favorable to industry may be emphasized and published simultaneously in multiple journals, amplifying the discourse of efficacy surrounding a drug [20]. Conversely, unfavorable findings may be discarded, suppressed, or not published [13, 15], since trials indicating low efficacy or safety risks may produce substantial financial losses.

Flacco et al. (2015) noted that biases can affect even randomized clinical trials, widely considered a high standard of reliability because they rely on the random allocation of subjects to compare an intervention with a control group [16]. From the standpoint of “economic rationality,” understood as central to large capitalist firms, the authors argue that it is reasonable to consider that pharmaceutical companies may adopt biases to facilitate approval and market consolidation of medicines with “high sales potential and financial return.”

The case of quetiapine, marketed as Seroquel by AstraZeneca and indicated for schizophrenia, bipolar disorder, and depressive disorder [21], illustrates how these dynamics can materialize. Documents obtained in legal proceedings indicated that, to protect a revenue stream exceeding US\$ 5 billion per year (Figure 1), the company allegedly manipulated studies to support claims that Seroquel offered advantages over a competitor in treating schizophrenia, despite inferior efficacy [15].

Investigations also suggested that AstraZeneca allegedly protected profits and exposed patients to risks by failing to disclose studies linking Seroquel use to weight gain and to increased risks of hyperglycemia and diabetes. Instead, physicians were allegedly misled by false promotional material and sales teams claiming that no studies associated the drug with these side effects [15]. Sustained by these practices, quetiapine became a major commercial success, totaling US\$ 36.7 billion in sales between 1999 and 2011 (Figure 1), the year its exclusivity patent expired.

After a lengthy legal process, in April 2010 AstraZeneca reached an agreement with the United States Department of Justice, committing to pay US\$ 520 million to resolve matters related to Seroquel [22]. That year, the drug was the fifth best-selling in the United States, cost approximately US\$ 4 per tablet [23], and generated US\$ 5.3 billion in sales for the company (Figure 1). In addition to the fine, the package insert was updated regarding indications and restrictions, allowing the product to remain on the global market.

Figure 1. Global annual revenue for Seroquel (quetiapine) (1999-2017, US\$). Source: AstraZeneca (2023).

Beyond shaping trial design, dissemination, and the visibility of results, corporate influence can also extend to how knowledge is written and presented in the scientific literature.

Ghostwriting

Alongside the manipulation of research and trials, the pharmaceutical sector has exerted substantial influence over the drafting and publication of scientific articles – one of the primary channels of communication between researchers and health professionals, with strong effects on medical opinion and the global definition of therapeutic practices. For the Danish physician and researcher Peter Christian Gøtzsche, scientific communication depends on trust: it is essential to trust information when planning experiments or treating patients [24]. Yet such reliability is not always assured.

One strategy described in this context is ghostwriting. Under this practice, articles addressing different aspects of a drug or treatment are produced by pharmaceutical companies themselves or by professional writers and contracted medical writing firms. Scientists, physicians, or academics with little or no involvement in the research, analysis, and writing are then invited to sign the papers, while the true authorship is omitted or relegated to minor acknowledgment or coauthorship.

By attaching “scientific” names to authorship, ghostwriting confers an appearance of independence and credibility, while “corporate” names are omitted to avoid associations with bias, distrust, and manipulation. Once published, these articles can be cited in promotional materials and within the peer-reviewed medical literature, contributing to dissemination and, consequently, to sales and profits for a specific drug [25].

Ghostwriting can also operate more subtly. It may be used to promote a new pathology or disorder that a drug is intended to treat [26], thereby preparing markets for commercialization; or, alternatively, to contest research unfavorable to pharmaceutical companies and their products [11]. The consequences can be harmful to patients and public health: by shaping prescribing practices, ghostwritten articles containing questionable claims or misinformation can mislead professionals and expose large numbers of patients to risk.

In the early 2000s, SmithKline Beecham (now GlaxoSmithKline) implemented the “CASPPER” program (“Case Study Publications for Peer Review”), which sought physicians with positive experiences prescribing the antidepressant paroxetine (Paxil). Through ghostwriters, the program financed the preparation of articles supporting the drug or countering competitors [27], and many of these texts were published as case studies.

A decade later, GlaxoSmithKline faced lawsuits linking paroxetine to violent behaviors, including suicides among children and adolescents [28]. In 2012, the company agreed to plead guilty and pay US\$ 3 billion to resolve charges brought by the United States Department of Justice involving, in addition to paroxetine, Wellbutrin and Avandia. The final sentencing report revealed that the company was responsible for drafting, publishing, and distributing misleading articles promoting the efficacy of paroxetine for treating depression in patients under 18 years of age [28]. Although substantial, the fine represented only a small fraction of the US\$ 27.9 billion obtained from sales of the three drugs during the agreement period [29], underscoring the profitability of perpetuating biases such as ghostwriting and one reason companies invest heavily in these practices.

Another case involved rofecoxib (Vioxx), manufactured by Merck. In 2008, litigation made thousands of confidential records public, and Joseph S. Ross led a team that analyzed approximately 20,000 documents. Ross et al. (2008) found that clinical trials and reviews of Vioxx had been drafted by Merck employees, who then invited external researchers and academics to appear as lead authors – often without disclosing the company’s funding [30].

Since its approval in May 1999, rofecoxib had been used by more than 80 million patients [31]. After years of studies and allegations associating its use with increased risks of myocardial infarction and stroke [32], Merck withdrew the drug from the market in September 2004. Eric Topol (2004) pointed to the company’s negligence in continuing, since 2001, to publish statements and articles drafted by employees and consultants asserting the drug’s cardiovascular safety.

Moreover, as reports of adverse effects multiplied, Merck continued to sponsor continuing medical education events intended to minimize concerns about cardiovascular safety [31]. The company also invested more than US\$ 100 million per year in direct-to-consumer advertising and maintained interest in revenues of approximately US\$ 2.5 billion annually [33], outweighing concerns about potential harms associated with the drug.

After extensive litigation, in 2007 Merck agreed to pay US\$ 4.85 billion to settle approximately 27,000 lawsuits brought by users or family members [34]. In 2011, the company also agreed to pay US\$ 950 million to settle criminal and civil allegations brought by the United States Department of Justice, which accused it of promoting the drug for conditions for which it had not yet been approved [35].

The episodes involving Merck and GlaxoSmithKline are not presented as isolated. Moffatt and Elliott (2007) and McHenry (2010) documented cases in which ghostwritten texts were linked to problematic therapies and deliberately shaped to benefit companies [26, 27]. In response to such concerns, the World Association of Medical Editors (WAME) expressed unease in 2005. In a statement titled “Ghost writing initiated by commercial companies” [36], the association emphasized the need for “honest authorship” so that editors and readers can trust publications and their authors’ commitments. Even so, according to the literature cited here, progress since then has been limited, and ghostwriting remains a recurrent practice in global pharmaceutical science communication, with negative effects on public and collective health.

Final considerations

The evidence assembled in this report converges on a central point: although the validation pathway for a medicine is formally structured to ensure safety and reliability, the reviewed literature indicates that, in certain contexts, evidence production may be permeated by biases aligned with corporate interests. These biases are not confined to isolated episodes; rather, they may constitute a repertoire of strategies beginning with the planning and conduct of research and trials – including methodological choices such as inferior comparators, inappropriate dosages, and placebo use – and extending into the selective circulation of knowledge through simultaneous and expanded publication of favorable results and the discarding, suppression, or non-publication of unfavorable findings. Within this dynamic, what is recognized as “evidence” may be shaped by mechanisms that strain scientific integrity and research ethics, with repercussions for how risks, benefits, and efficacy are perceived and communicated.

Influence becomes even more incisive when it reaches the sphere of authorship and scientific writing. By concealing corporate authors and mobilizing “scientific” names to confer credibility, ghostwriting reconfigures the appearance of independence of articles that circulate widely among health professionals and may be incorporated into peer-reviewed literature and promotional materials. By linking the manipulation and concealment of evidence to strategies of publication and authorship, this report shows how these mechanisms can reverberate through clinical practice and collective health, precisely because they affect the informational base that underpins therapeutic decisions and medical guidance. Ultimately, the cases and studies discussed reinforce the need to treat trust in scientific communication as a concrete problem – shaped by disputes and interests – rather than as a guaranteed presupposition.

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